

CATALYTIC FORMATION OF METHANE FROM CARBON MONOXIDE AND HYDROGEN. PART VI. ON THE POISONING BY CARBON DEPOSITION.

BY K. M. CHAKRAVARTY.

It has been shown that the reaction $2\text{CO} = \text{C} + \text{CO}_2$ is catalysed both by nickel and nickel carbide. The reaction $\text{CO} + 3\text{H}_2 = \text{CH}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ is accelerated by nickel. Poisoning in both the cases is mainly due to the deposited carbon adsorbed on the surface. In the latter case the carbon deposition is due to reaction $\text{CO} + \text{H}_2 = \text{C} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ as well.

The fact that nickel catalysts lose activity due to carbon deposition is well known. The deposited carbon may be absorbed on the nickel particles or may simply form a layer on the catalytic surface. In the process of carbon deposition, nickel may also undergo carbide formation. The point therefore arises as to how far each of these affects the activity of the catalyst and whether nickel carbide also has any catalytic influence.

Ruff and co-workers (*Metallurgie*, 1912, **9**, 143; *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1914, **88**, 386) have found that in molten nickel carbon is dissolved to the extent required by the formula Ni_3C . This solubility remains constant till the boiling point 2075° is reached showing thereby that a carbide is formed. Recent investigations (Meyer and Scheffer, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1927, **46**, 1; Bahr and Bahr, *Ber.*, 1928, **61**, 2177; 1930, **63**, 99; Tutiya, *Bull. Inst. Phys. Chem. Res. Japan*, 1931, **10**, 951; Schmidt, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1933, **216**, 83; Jacobsen and Westgren, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1933, **B20**, 361; Hedvali and Sandford, *ibid.*, 1935, **B29**, 455) have shown that this carbide is also formed when carbon monoxide is passed over reduced nickel at about 260° . No carbide is, however, formed at 700° (Meyer and Scheffer, *loc. cit.*) and at 500° only 2% of the total carbon deposited combined with nickel (Bahr and Bahr, *loc. cit.*). This shows the exothermic nature of the reaction. It has been represented by Bahr and Bahr by the equation

According to Tutiya the heat of reaction is 46.4 Cals.

This formation of the carbide has been definitely established both by physical and chemical tests. Complete solution of the product in hydrochloric acid giving hydrocarbon gases indicated clearly the absence of free carbon in the sample and the formation of carbide. The magnetic property indicated the absence of free nickel. The estimation of carbon and nickel in

the sample has established that a carbide of the formula Ni_3C was formed. The X-ray diagram which was different from that of carbon and nickel also proved that a definite compound was obtained.

The heat of reaction whereby carbon combines with nickel to yield nickel carbide has recently been redetermined by Roth (*Arch. Eisenhüttenw.*, 1929-30, 3, 339; *Stahl. u. Eisen*, 1929, 49, 1763) giving the figure -9.2 ($\pm 10\%$) Cals. This shows the endothermic nature of the reaction in question and explains why a nickel carbon solution containing 6.37% of carbon (Ni_3C) on being suddenly cooled by dropping into cold water did not show any line for carbide in an X-ray diagram. The extent of stability of this carbide formed at a much lower temperature has therefore been examined by Bahr and Bahr (*loc. cit.*). On heating the carbide in an atmosphere of nitrogen above 380-400°, liberation of free carbon has been detected by the action of hydrochloric acid. The decomposition temperature, however, depends upon the condition of preparation (Bahr and Bahr, *loc. cit.*). A sample has been found to be unaffected even at 500° when heated for 14 hours. Generally, however, these carbide preparations are stable up to 400°. This stability up to a temperature of 400° in an atmosphere of nitrogen of the nickel carbide, formed by the action of carbon monoxide upon nickel, suggests that it will show no tendency to decompose at least at 400° in an atmosphere of carbon monoxide.

The investigation of Cleminson and Briscoe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2148) has revealed that carbon monoxide does not dissociate at or below 400° when glass forms the contact material. From Bahr and Bahr's paper it is also clear that the fission of carbon monoxide does not take place at 250°-270° on a nickel carbide surface. From their paper it is also true that the carbide formation must have been complete after 20 hours at temperatures higher than 270°. Since the deposition of carbon continued even after 90 hours, it is evident that the nickel carbide formed was catalysing the reaction in question at temperatures higher than 270°, the catalytic effect of glass being negligible below 400°.

The question arises as to whether nickel also can act as a catalyst for this reaction in the temperature range in which the carbide is stable. The fact that nickel can catalyse the carbon deposition at temperatures higher than those at which the carbide decomposes, indicates that it will also perform the same operation in the lower temperature range as well, provided a suitable nickel preparation can be obtained which will not be converted into the carbide in the temperature region in question. Hedvall and Sandford (*loc. cit.*) have succeeded in preparing such a nickel catalyst. On keeping their catalyst at 260° for 460 hours in a current of carbon monoxide, 1 c.c.

per minute only, 3% of the nickel were converted into the carbide. When tried at 350° for 190 hours there was carbon deposition but no carbide was practically formed. But the fact that the reaction $2\text{CO} = \text{C} + \text{CO}_2$ was continually catalysed by this nickel preparation is a clear indication of the reaction being catalysed by nickel from 260°-360°. According to Clemjason and Briscoe (*loc. cit.*) this reaction just begins at 360° on purified sugar charcoal. Therefore, the catalytic action of deposited carbon, if any, will be negligible. It was also noticed that the reaction rate suddenly increased at the Curie points of the original nickel catalysts. This lent additional support to the view that in experiments of Hedvall and Sandford nickel and not the carbide was the main catalyser; otherwise these temperatures would have widely differed. Their figures for the Curie points etc. are quoted below.

Catalyst.	Curie point.	Temperature of sudden change in the reaction rate.
Ni (ii)	354-359°	354°-359°
Ni (iii)	364-370	364-370

Taylor (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 593) has found that at about 270° the adsorption of carbon monoxide on nickel catalyst is irreversible presumably being attached to the nickel surface as Ni_3C and NiO . At lower temperature the sorption is reversible probably due to the formation of adsorption compounds or to van der Waals absorption. Since particles of different degrees of activity exist on a nickel catalyst surface, it is impossible that in the temperature range 240°-300° for example, the retention of carbon will be mainly due to the formation of both nickel carbide and adsorption compounds. As a matter of fact, Horiba and Ri (*Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1928, 3, 18; *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1932, 51, 641) have shown that the retardation of the reaction

on the nickel surface is initially due to absorption of carbon monoxide but from 240°-300° it is due to the formation of nickel carbide and adsorption compound. But since a nickel surface (Bahr and Bahr, *loc. cit.*) continues to catalyse the reaction even when it is completely converted into carbide suggests that adsorbed carbon is the main poison. Bhatnagar and co-workers (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1929, 3, 53) have proved that chemical forces are involved in this process of adsorption. They have noticed that the paramagnetic nickel becomes diamagnetic on being adsorbed on carbon particles. So due to adsorption the active nickel particles are not only covered with carbon

particles but also their unsaturation is lowered. As a consequence the poisoning due to adsorption will be more pronounced in comparison with that due to the carbide formation. From Meyer and Scheffer's paper (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1927, **46**, 1) the inert nature of the carbon nickel mixture obtained by the action of carbon monoxide on nickel at 700° is evident, for like carbon the product was unaffected by the action of hydrochloric acid while both nickel and its carbide are readily soluble.

It, therefore, appears clear that both nickel and its carbide can catalyse the reaction

According to Horiba and Ri (*loc. cit.*) the poisoning is partly due to carbide formation. So the activity of the carbide surface produced from a nickel one will have a comparatively low activity. But adsorbed carbon is mainly responsible for poisoning. More or less similar conclusions can also be drawn for the catalysis of the reaction by a nickel catalyst.

Sabatier and Senderens (Sabatier and Reid, "Catalysis in Organic Chemistry," 1923, p. 144) noticed that while catalysing the above reaction at 250° using as reactants one part by volume of carbon monoxide and three parts by volume of hydrogen, the nickel catalyst was slightly carburised. The complete solubility of this product in hydrochloric acid indicated that nickel carbide was formed and no free carbon was deposited. The fact that the activity of the catalyst was not appreciably altered due to carbide formation shows that the formation of carbide to a small extent, which is realisable when the reaction is carried on below 250°, does not affect the activity to an appreciable degree. But when carried out above 250°, the carbide formation becomes more and more considerable and has a deliterious effect upon the catalyst. Under the above circumstances, however, the activity remains undiminished when a 5:1 mixture instead of a 3:1 of hydrogen and carbon monoxide is used. Evidently this is due to the diluent effect of hydrogen which leads to a retardation of the reaction.

An analysis of the experimental data of Litkenhous and Mann (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1937, **29**, 934) throws more light in this connection. In the following table are given the logarithms of the equilibrium constants of

a number of reactions calculated from their experimenal data. They passed a mixture of nickel carbonyl vapour and hydrogen through the reaction chamber at atmospheric and higher pressures. The composition of the initial gas mixture and the rate of passing were the same throughout the whole series of experiments.

TABLE I.

Reaction	at 350°	at 400°.	
1. $2\text{CO} + 2\text{H}_2 = \text{CH}_4 + \text{C}$	(1) 7.0166	(1) 5.4124	
	(2) 6.5392	(2) 5.0308	
	(3) 7.1225	(3) 3.4178	
	$K_p = \frac{p_{\text{CH}_4} \times p_{\text{CO}_2}}{p_{\text{CO}}^2 \times p_{\text{H}_2}^2}$	6.4120	3.4268
		6.9462	3.4537
			3.4401
2. $\text{CO} + 3\text{H}_2 = \text{CH}_4 + \text{H}_2$	(1) 5.7040	(1) 4.3385	
	(2) 5.2781	(2) 3.9862	
	(3) 4.7426	(3) 3.2748	
	$K_p = \frac{p_{\text{CH}_4} \times p_{\text{H}_2}}{p_{\text{CO}} \times p_{\text{H}_2}^3}$	5.1408	3.3109
		5.6032	3.3868
			3.3888
3. $2\text{CO} = \text{C} + \text{CO}_2$	(1) 5.2330	(1) 4.1619	
	(2) 4.8700	(2) 3.8510	
	(3) 5.3475	(3) 2.2169	
	$K_p = \frac{p_{\text{CO}_2}}{p_{\text{CO}}^2}$	4.8343	2.1776
		5.2284	2.1725
			2.2003

(1) Chipman, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1932, **24**, 1013.

(2) Reinders, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, **130**, 405.

(3) Litkenhous & Mann, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1937, **29**, 934.

TABLE I (contd.).

4. $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO} = \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2$	(1) 1'3126	(1) 1'0739
$K_p = \frac{p_{\text{CO}_2} \times p_{\text{H}_2}}{p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \times p_{\text{CO}}}$	(2) 1'2611	(2) 1'0446
	(3) 1'3785	(3) 0'1433
	1'2624	0'1156
	1'3653	0'1361
		0'1024
5. $\text{CO} + \text{H}_2 = \text{C} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	(1) 3'9203	(1) 3'0877
$K_p = \frac{p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{p_{\text{CO}} \times p_{\text{H}_2}}$	(2) 3'6089	(2) 3'8064
	(3) 3'9678	(3) 2'0738
	3'5719	2'0620
	3'8630	2'0362
		2'0979

From the above table one finds curiously that though all the reactions generally reached equilibrium at 350° , practically none of them reached that stage at 400° . Evidently the nickel particles were seriously poisoned at 400° . There was carbon deposition in all the experiments from 240° to 400° and as a matter of fact the deposition was the greatest at the lowest temperature *viz.* 250° and the least at the highest temperature *viz.* 400° . That this was so will be clear from Table II and is in accordance with the thermodynamic requirement.

TABLE II.

Temp.	250°	300	350	400
C deposited (mole)	0'0001057	0'0000969	0'0000885	0'0000867

So it is evident that poisoning was not proportional to the amount of carbon deposition but depended rather on how the deposition occurred. It has been concluded before that nickel carbide becomes unstable above 400° . The nickel preparation of Hedvall and Sandford (*loc. cit.*) did not yield the nickel carbide at 360° though there was carbon deposition on passing carbon monoxide over it. Bahr and Bahr (*loc. cit.*) have shown that the combined carbon is readily converted into methane at $180\text{--}380^\circ$ by the action of hydrogen, whereas free carbon remains unchanged under these conditions. Their gas analysis data are as CO_2 , 0.3 ; S.K.W., 0.2 ; O_2 , 0.0 ; CO , 0.2 ; H_2 , 2.4 ; CH_4 , 28.6 ; C_2H_6 , 3.2 ; and N_2 , 65.1 (als Spülgas) Total, 100.0.

It therefore follows that at 400° and higher temperatures the carbide formation will be more or less impossible where the reacting gas instead of being only carbon monoxide is a mixture of this gas with hydrogen. At lower temperatures, however, the carbon deposition producing nickel carbide will increase gradually while the free carbon deposition will gradually decrease. So, it is clear from the data of Litkenhous and Mann given above that carbon deposition which leads to carbide formation does not affect the activity of nickel catalyst for the reaction in question to an extent as free carbon deposition even in smaller doses does. Here the temperature being 400° the question of sintering also comes in. But our experiments with simple nickel catalyst described in a previous paper (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1931, 37, 775) show that this effect is rather small.

Kubokawa (*Rev. Phys. Chem. Japan*, 1938, 12, 40) studied the decomposition of methane on nickel surface at 500°. The activity of the catalyst became constant after it had decreased to certain extent inspite of the accumulation of carbon particles. This shows that the first one or two layers of carbon are responsible for the poisoning and these are evidently the adsorbed carbon layers. The existence of nickel carbide at such a high temperature appears to be impossible. Schmidt (*loc. cit.*) has shown that no carbide is formed by the decomposition of methane over nickel even at 250° though his nickel catalyst was found to yield carbide at 240°-250° by the action of carbon monoxide and at 180°-200° by the action of acetylene.

Eventually one can conclude that for the reaction $\text{CO} + 3\text{H}_2 = \text{CH}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$, nickel is the most active catalyst. Nickel carbide does not poison the catalyst to the extent as adsorbed carbon does. It is also possible in view of Kubokawa's data that unadsorbed carbon particles will not also affect the above reaction to an appreciable extent.

From the behaviour of sugar charcoal-nickel catalysts described in some previous papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1925-26, 2, 150, 157; 1927, 4, 431) we have noticed that sintering is checked by sugar carbon acting as a support material and is not a serious poison. The catalysts generally were not highly active. The activity decreased with an increase in the concentration of sugar carbon. Free nickel was present in those catalysts and was indicated by the formation of nickel carbonyl in an atmosphere of the reacting gases.

But the fact that the deposition of carbon particles on a nickel surface in the process of catalysis affects the activity seriously is partly because

of the fact that the deposition occurs selectively on the most active particles from which the tracks of the reaction on the catalyst surface start and partly due to the fact that under the circumstances the deposition of nickel particles upon the carbon particles is almost impossible.

The carbon deposition which poisons the nickel catalyst has so far been ascribed to the reaction $2\text{CO}=\text{C}+\text{CO}_2$. From our experimental data of a forthcoming paper it is clear that the deposition of carbon may as well be due to the reaction $\text{CO}+\text{H}_2=\text{C}+\text{H}_2\text{O}$. This can also be inferred from the experimental data of Litkenhous and Mann (*loc. cit.*) and has been dealt with fully in a letter to be published shortly in the Journal of the Industrial & Engineering Chemistry.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY.

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